

OPEN PROTOCOLS

in Diamond Open Access Publishing

Background
Rationale
Aims of the study
Hypotheses
Methodology
Analysis plans

A Research Protocol is a detailed document prepared before conducting a study.

→ It is often written as part of ethics and funding applications.

→ In medical and educational fields, it may be published as a separate article type.

WHY SHOULD DIAMOND OA JOURNALS ENCOURAGE SHARING RESEARCH PROTOCOLS ?

Transparency

It creates a foundation of openness that enhances credibility of findings and allows for proper verification.

Reproducibility

It makes it easier to replicate and build upon published research, improving scientific advancement.

Collaboration

It attracts new collaborators or facilitates collaboration across labs.

Priority of discovery

It establishes priority of research, reducing the risk of being "scooped".

WHAT CAN YOU DO AS A PUBLISHER ?

1

Define **policies** for the availability of research protocols.

2

Encourage sharing protocols in **public repositories** that use **PIDs**.

3

Display this information on the journal website.

Reporting standard template

[Journal's title] is committed to serving the research community by ensuring that all articles include enough information to allow others to reproduce the work.

A submitted manuscript should contain sufficient detail and references to permit reviewers and, subsequently, readers to verify the claims presented in it – e.g. provide complete details of the methods used, including time frames, etc.

Authors are required to review the standards available for many research applications from Equator Network and use those that are relevant for the reported research applications.

The deliberate presentation of false claims is a violation of ethical standards.